

Comparing CoNDERC Decay Heat Data with Serpent 2 and FISPACT-II Simulations

S. Portolan^{1,2,*}, D. Rochman³, L. Giot⁴, A. Vasiliev¹, H. Ferroukhi¹, A. Pautz^{1,2}

¹PSI Center for Nuclear Engineering and Science, Paul Scherrer Institut, 5232 Villigen PSI, Switzerland;

²EPFL, Rte Cantonale, Lausanne, Switzerland; ³Nagra, Hardstrasse 73, Wettingen, Switzerland;

⁴Subatech, CNRS/IN2P3, Institut Mines Telecom Atlantique, Nantes University, 44307 Nantes, France

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ABSTRACT

Decay heat plays a critical role in spent nuclear fuel (SNF) management, affecting accident scenarios, interim and long-term storage. Because direct measurements of decay heat for complete fuel assemblies are limited, or non available for cooling times of less than one year, validation efforts for short cooling times rely primarily on fission pulse experiments. For the results shown in this study the cooling times range between 1s and 12'000s or 100'000s for Dicken's data and Tobias' data, respectively. In this work, experimental decay heat data available through the CoNDERC database are compared with simulations performed using Serpent 2 and FISPACT-II. FISPACT-II, previously validated against CoNDERC data, is used as a reference for code-to-code assessment. Additionally, Serpent 2 simulations are repeated for different nuclear data libraries, including ENDF/B-VII.1, -VIII.0, JEFF-3.1.1, -3.3, -4.0, and JENDL-4.0, -5, to explore their impact on decay heat and major contributors.

Results show generally good agreement between simulations and measurements for the selected nuclides present in the study (²³⁵U and ²³⁹Pu from Tobias meta-analysis, ²⁴¹Pu and ²³⁵U from Dickens experiments), with most simulation results corresponding with the respective measured values, within the reported experimental uncertainties. Code-to-code comparisons demonstrated strong consistency between Serpent 2 and FISPACT-II. Differences among results obtained with different nuclear data libraries are mainly observed at cooling times shorter than 200s, particularly for JEFF-3.1.1 and JENDL-5, highlighting the sensitivity of decay heat to decay and fission yield data.

Keywords: Decay Heat, Fission Pulse Measurements, Validation, Nuclear Data

1. INTRODUCTION

Decay heat is a paramount quantity throughout the nuclear fuel cycle, from in-reactor operations and accidents scenarios to core unloading, fuel transport, and storage. In particular, an accurate estimation of decay heat can reduce the number of required transport casks and, consequently, the cost of fuel transport and following storage [1]. One way to estimate decay heat in spent nuclear fuel (SNF) is through the Best-Estimate Plus Uncertainties (BEPU) approach [1]. To support such an approach, the codes capable of depletion and decay calculations must be thoroughly validated.

However, the publicly available decay heat measurements for complete fuel assemblies [2, 3] only extend down to approximately 1.5 years after shutdown, leaving the first year uncovered. As a consequence, validation of simulation codes for short cooling times relies on fission pulse measurements, which are obtained by irradiating small samples of a single nuclide, in order to study the decay heat produced, ideally, by a single fission event. In this study, the fission pulse measurements available in the fission section of the CoNDERC website [4] are compared with simulated results obtained using Serpent 2 [5] and FISPACT-II [6]. The latter has already been validated against the data in the CoNDERC compilation [7], including tests with different nuclear data libraries and input options. Therefore, FISPACT-II

*sofia.portolan@psi.ch

is used as a reference for code-to-code comparison, relying on the FISPACT-II input files provided in the CoNDERC database.

The second part of this work compares simulated decay heat values obtained with different nuclear data libraries. This analysis is particularly relevant because, in recent years, total absorption spectroscopy (TAS) measurements have led to updates in the decay data of several fission products [8]. These updates aim to mitigate the so-called "*Pandemonium Effect*" [9, 10], which produces a systematic underestimation of the beta feeding, resulting in an overestimation of the gamma contribution to total decay heat.

2. CONDERC DECAY HEAT MEASUREMENTS

The CoNDERC database contains several sets of data for many different applications, including, but not limited to, decay heat measurements from fission events [4, 7]. Fission pulse decay heat measurements are experiments aimed at measuring the heat released by, ideally, a single fission event, in a single nuclide [7, 11–14]. Fission pulse measurements are particularly valuable for evaluating the decay calculation capabilities of codes, since in this configuration the dependency on cross sections is removed, and the results depend only on fission yields and decay data.

In fission pulse experiments, a highly enriched sample of the nuclide of interest is irradiated in an experimental reactor and then rapidly transferred to a detector system; in Dickens' experimental setup, irradiation time range from 1s up to 100s [11]. There exist also non-pulse measurements where the irradiation times range from a few seconds to several months; a small number of these were performed using a calorimeter [15–17]. While pulse experiments are directly relevant for validating the depletion/decay capabilities of codes, non-pulse measurements are generally more representative of practical applications.

Data from several reports have been extracted and made available on the CoNDERC website. The dataset used in this study is very similar to the one used previously for the FISPACT-II validation study in Table 2 of [7]. Among all the measurements, the results attributed to Tobias are labelled with the method "*Stat.*". This is because the reported values were obtained by selecting and fitting the results of multiple experimental campaigns. In practice, Tobias performed a meta-analysis of the state-of-the-art measurements available at the time, producing a consistent set of decay-heat values and associated uncertainties for ^{235}U and ^{239}Pu . Although these are not direct measurements, for consistency and simplicity, they will also be referred to as measurements in this text.

3. CODES

3.1. FISPACT-II

FISPACT-II is an enhanced multi-physics, inventory, and source-term code system providing a wide variety of advanced, predictive, spectral, and temporal simulation methods employing the most up-to-date and complete nuclear data forms for both neutron and charged-particle interactions [6].

FISPACT-II is based on a solver developed at Lawrence Livermore Laboratory called LSODE, which uses the backward differentiation formula method, also known as Gear's method. It was validated for standard ^{235}U , ^{239}Pu , ^{241}Pu thermal pulses against several experiments, such as Dickens, Schier, and Tobias [11–14]. Furthermore, FISPACT-II has already been validated for all the measurements present on the CoNDERC website [4]. The version used for this study is the Release 3.00.

3.2. Serpent 2

The second code used to model and simulate decay heat based on the CoNDERC data is Serpent 2 [5]. Serpent 2 is a versatile three-dimensional continuous-energy neutron and photon Monte Carlo transport code, developed since 2004 at the VTT Technical Research Centre of Finland. Serpent 2 supports three-

dimensional (3D) geometry as well as two-dimensional (2D) models.

Serpent 2 employs two different methods by default for depletion and decay calculations. During the depletion phase, in burnup calculations, Serpent uses Chebyshev Rational Approximation Method (CRAM) of order 14, while for the decay phase, it uses Transmutation Trajectory Analysis (TTA).

Serpent 2 was selected for this work due to its flexibility: it is capable of simulating external irradiation problems, such as fission pulse experiments, as well as solving neutron transport and fuel depletion calculations, and was also already used in such fission pulse measurements [18]. The version used in this study is 2.2.0.

4. MODELLING

As the two codes differ in how the irradiation and decay phases are treated, the modelling approaches are not identical. For the input files of FISPACT-II, the CoNDERC website provides example input files that can be modified depending on the application (*e.g.*, pulse or non-pulse measurements) and the nuclide to be irradiated. Additional modelling instructions are also available in the FISPACT-II validation study [7].

In the case of Serpent 2, its primary capability is neutron transport, but it can also simulate external irradiation sources, by using the "set nps" card. The Serpent 2 inputs follow the same general logic as the FISPACT-II models. The nuclide is irradiated using a mono-energetic neutron source at the same energy reported in the FISPACT-II validation study. The results are then normalised by setting the neutron flux to the same magnitude reported in the FISPACT-II inputs. The Serpent 2 "set transmurea" card is used to specify fission as the only reaction included in the burnup calculation. To obtain results for different nuclear data libraries, the corresponding input lines relative to cross sections, fission yields, and decay data were replaced to read the data for the same selected nuclear data library.

5. RESULTS

The main objective of this study is to first compare CoNDERC decay heat measurements with simulation results obtained using Serpent 2 and FISPACT-II, and second, to evaluate consistency between the two codes. In addition, Serpent 2 results generated with different nuclear data libraries are analysed.

Due to space limitations, only a subset of the full dataset is presented here. The focus is on nuclides relevant for light water reactor fuels, namely ^{239}Pu , ^{241}Pu , and ^{235}U undergoing thermal fission.

5.1. Code-to-experiments and code-to-code comparisons

This subsection presents qualitative comparisons between simulation results and measurements for the thermal fission pulse of ^{235}U , ^{239}Pu , and ^{241}Pu . Figures 1-2-3-4 show the time evolution of decay heat in MeV/fission, reported as total decay heat, and the gamma and beta components. The measurement uncertainties correspond to 1σ . All the results in this section are obtained using the nuclear data library ENDF/B-VII.1 [19].

For the cases shown in this study, all components (total, beta, and gamma) were measured, which is not true for all datasets in the database, as some experiments report only a subset of decay heat components.

Figures 1 and 3 show the time evolution of the decay heat from $\sim 1\text{s}$ after irradiation up to $\sim 10^5\text{s}$. The measurements used in both cases were reported by Tobias [14]. Both Serpent 2 and FISPACT-II tend to underestimate the total decay heat and the beta component between approximately 4-10s, and 500- 10^3s for ^{239}Pu , and between roughly 1.5s- 10^3s (and slightly beyond) for ^{235}U .

Figures 2 and 4 show the evolution of decay heat from $\sim 2.7\text{s}$ to $\sim 10^4\text{s}$, using the measurements reported by Dickens [11]. In this case, a slight underestimate of the decay heat can be observed for ^{241}Pu ,

Figure 1. Comparison of Tobias measurements [14] with Serpent 2 and FISPACT-II results for ^{239}Pu using ENDF/B-VII.1

Figure 2. Comparison of Dickens measurements [11] with Serpent 2 and FISPACT-II results for ^{241}Pu using ENDF/B-VII.1

Figure 3. Comparison of Tobias measurements [14] with Serpent 2 and FISPACT-II results for ^{235}U using ENDF/B-VII.1

Figure 4. Comparison of Dickens measurements [11] with Serpent 2 and FISPACT-II results for ^{235}U using ENDF/B-VII.1

although both Serpent 2 and FISPACT-II curves generally remain within the measurements' uncertainty for each time step, with only a few exceptions.

For Dickens ^{235}U data [11], both codes remain within the measurement uncertainty up to around 10^3s . Beyond this point, both codes temporarily overestimate the decay heat.

An additional consideration can be made by comparing Figures 3-4. Since the same nuclide is involved, the Serpent 2 and FISPACT-II results were obtained using the same simulation method. However, the overestimation observed in Dickens case for cooling times around $10^3\text{-}10^4\text{s}$ does not appear in Tobias, and, conversely, the underestimation visible in Tobias up to 10^3s is not present in Dickens' case.

The following Figures 5-6-7-8 present a comparison of calculated (C) against measured (E) results, along with a code-to-code comparison using FISPACT-II as a reference. Figures 5-6 show results for ^{239}Pu and ^{241}Pu , while Figures 7-8 show those for ^{235}U . Relative measurement uncertainties are indicated in pink.

For Tobias data, the first data points exhibit high experimental uncertainties, exceeding 40% for ^{239}Pu and around 15% for ^{235}U , before decreasing below 10% after a few seconds. In Dickens' data, uncertainties decrease from roughly 6% to below 3% then rise again above 6% after about 7000s. When con-

Figure 5. Comparison of Tobias measurements [14] with Serpent 2 and FISPACT-II results for ^{239}Pu .

Figure 6. Comparison of Dickens measurements [11] with Serpent 2 and FISPACT-II results for ^{241}Pu .

Figure 7. Comparison of Tobias measurements [14] with Serpent 2 and FISPACT-II results for ^{235}U .

Figure 8. Comparison of Dickens measurements [11] with Serpent 2 and FISPACT-II results for ^{235}U .

Considering Tobias results for ^{239}Pu after 3s the relative uncertainty is approximately 7.5%, then decreases to less than 2.5% to later increase again to around 3.5%. A similar trend is observed for ^{235}U .

The C/E values obtained with the Serpent 2 and FISPACT-II codes fall within the 2σ range of the relative measurement uncertainty for both ^{239}Pu and ^{241}Pu , with C/E values ranging from approximately 0.89 to 1.04, and from 0.96 to 1.02, respectively. The behaviour is different for ^{235}U , for which four C/E values in Figure 7 lie outside the 2σ range of the relative measurement uncertainty. Additionally, in the case of ^{235}U , the C/E values range from 0.87 to 1.04 for the Tobias measurements and from 0.95 to 1.07 for the Dickens measurements. In general, as shown in Table I for the nuclear data library ENDF/B-VII.1, the mean C/E for Figure 5 is 0.976, for Figure 6 is 0.988, for Figure 7 is 0.967, and for Figure 8 is 1.012.

Relative to code-to-code comparisons, green markers represent the FISPACT-II/Serpent 2 ratio. In particular, Serpent 2 results are close to FISPACT-II: the average ratio is 1.001, 0.996, 0.997, and 0.997 for Figures 5-6-7-8. The largest deviation between the two codes is around 1% for the cases shown in these figures.

5.2. Comparison with multiple nuclear data libraries

In this section, the decay heat measurements are compared with the simulation results obtained using different nuclear data libraries. The nuclear data libraries considered are: ENDF/B-VII.1, ENDF/B-VIII.0, JEFF-3.1.1, JEFF-3.3, JEFF-4.0, JENDL-4.0, and JENDL-5.

Figures 9-10-11-12 show results for fission pulse decay heat measurements of ^{239}Pu , ^{241}Pu , and ^{235}U . For all nuclides, the behaviour of the different nuclear data libraries becomes relatively consistent after approximately 10^2s after irradiation. However, noticeable differences emerge at cooling times shorter than 10^3s , particularly for JEFF-3.1.1 and JENDL-5¹, which show differences of up to 8.1% and 9.0%, respectively, compared to the simulation results obtained with the other nuclear data libraries.

Figure 9. Comparison of Tobias measurements [14] with Serpent 2 results for ^{239}Pu using multiple nuclear data libraries. Including only total decay heat and gamma contribution.

Figure 10. Comparison of Dickens measurements [11] with Serpent 2 results for ^{241}Pu using multiple nuclear data libraries. Including only total decay heat and gamma contribution.

Figure 11. Comparison of Tobias measurements [14] with Serpent 2 results for ^{235}U using multiple nuclear data libraries. Including only total decay heat and gamma contribution.

Figure 12. Comparison of Dickens measurements [11] with Serpent 2 results for ^{235}U using multiple nuclear data libraries. Including only total decay heat and gamma contribution.

For ^{239}Pu , JENDL-5 predicts decay heat values above those of other libraries from around 6s up to roughly 300s, while the gamma contribution obtained using JEFF-3.1.1 remains lower than that of other libraries from around 6s up to approximately 10^4s . A similar trend of the gamma contribution using JEFF-3.1.1 is also observed for ^{241}Pu . Notably, for ^{235}U the results obtained with different nuclear data libraries show good agreement, with discrepancies limited to the first 100s of cooling time. After 100s of cooling time, the relative difference between the C/E of different libraries is less than 3.5%.

The average C/E for the total decay heat is reported in Table I.

Nuclide	ENDF/B-VII.1	ENDF/B-VIII.0	JEFF-3.1.1	JEFF-3.3	JEFF-4.0	JENDL-4	JENDL-5
²³⁹ Pu Tobias	0.976	0.976	0.978	0.993	0.992	0.988	0.998
²⁴¹ Pu Dickens	0.988	0.987	0.978	0.979	0.986	0.993	0.983
²³⁵ U Tobias	0.967	0.966	0.978	0.978	0.980	0.978	0.975
²³⁵ U Dickens	1.012	1.009	1.022	1.014	1.015	1.015	1.020

Table I. Average C/E results for different nuclear data libraries.

6. CONCLUSIONS

In this study, the decay capabilities of Serpent 2 and FISPACT-II were analysed using data available in the CoNDERC database. First, both codes were compared against decay heat measurements, and then to each other, with FISPACT-II serving as a reference. The second part focused on the impact of the nuclear data library on the simulated decay heat, motivated by the recent TAS measurements that updated the decay data of several fission products.

Since the CoNDERC database contains thousands of measurements covering multiple nuclides and both thermal and fast fission, only a selection of nuclides, relevant for LWR studies, was included, namely ²³⁹Pu, ²⁴¹Pu, and ²³⁵U.

Section 5.1 presented the comparison between the code results and the experimental fission-pulse measurements of Tobias and Dickens. Beyond a first qualitative analysis, a detailed evaluation of the C/E time evolution was performed. In general, both Serpent 2 and FISPACT-II showed good agreement with the measurements, with only a restricted number of C/E values outside of the uncertainty bounds of 2σ of the experimental data. A direct code-to-code comparison also showed good consistency. The average code-to-code (C/C) ratio between Serpent 2 and FISPACT-II was approximately 1.001, 0.996, 0.997, and 0.997, for ²³⁹Pu, ²⁴¹Pu, and the two ²³⁵U cases, respectively, with a maximum deviation of approximately 1%.

Section 5.2 compared the decay heat predictions obtained using different nuclear data libraries. Most libraries agreed within approximately 200s after irradiation. However, noticeable differences appeared for JENDL-5 and JEFF-3.1.1 for ²³⁹Pu and ²⁴¹Pu.

NOTES

¹A correction has been issued for the fission yield library in JENDL-5. However, this corrected version was not used in the current study, as it is not yet publicly available. The version used for this study corresponds to update-8 of the JENDL-5 fission yield library released on Jul. 13, 2022.

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REFERENCES

- [1] Dimitri Rochman et al. "An introduction to Spent Nuclear Fuel decay heat for Light Water Reactors: a review from the NEA WPNCS". In: *EPJ Nuclear Sci. Technol.* 10 (2024), p. 9. DOI: 10.1051/epjn/2024010.

- [2] EPRI. *Spent Fuel Decay Heat Measurements at Clab: Description of Decay Heat Measurements from 2003 - 2021 Under EPRI-SKB Collaboration*. Tech. rep. 3002026549. EPRI, Palo Alto, CA, 2024. URL: <https://www.epri.com/research/products/000000003002026549>.
- [3] F Sturek et al. *Measurements of decay heat in spent nuclear fuel at the Swedish interim storage facility, Clab*. Tech. rep. R-05-62. SE-102 40 Stockholm Sweden: Svensk Kärnbränslehantering AB, Dec. 2006. URL: <https://www.skb.com/publication/1472024>.
- [4] Ian Gauld. *Data Compilation and Analysis of Fission Product Decay Heat Experiments*. URL: https://www-nds.iaea.org/media/docs/fission/Gauld_SummaryReport_2019.pdf.
- [5] Jaakko Leppänen et al. "Status of Serpent Monte Carlo code in 2024". In: *EPJ Nuclear Sci. Technol.* 11 (2025), p. 3. DOI: 10.1051/epjn/2024031. URL: <https://doi.org/10.1051/epjn/2024031>.
- [6] J.-Ch. Sublet et al. "FISPACT-II: An Advanced Simulation System for Activation, Transmutation and Material Modelling". In: *Nuclear Data Sheets* 139 (2017). Special Issue on Nuclear Reaction Data, pp. 77–137. ISSN: 0090-3752. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.nds.2017.01.002>.
- [7] Michael Fleming et al. *Validation of FISPACT-II Decay Heat and Inventory Predictions for Fission Events*. June 2015. DOI: 10.13140/RG.2.1.1003.8168.
- [8] A.-A. Zakari-Issoufou et al. "Results of fission products β decay properties measurement performed with a total absorption spectrometer". In: *EPJ Web of Conferences* 66 (2014), p. 10019. DOI: 10.1051/epjconf/20146610019.
- [9] John Hardy et al. "The essential decay of pandemonium: A demonstration of errors in complex beta-decay schemes". In: *Physics Letters B* 71 (Nov. 1977), pp. 307–310. DOI: 10.1016/0370-2693(77)90223-4.
- [10] M. Estienne et al. "Recent advances in beta decay measurements". In: *EPJ Nuclear Sci. Technol.* 4 (2018), p. 24. DOI: 10.1051/epjn/2018034.
- [11] J. K. Dickens et al. *Fission Product Energy Release for Times Following Thermal-Neutron Fission of ^{235}U Between 2 and 14000 Seconds*. Technical Report ORNL/NUREG-14. Oak Ridge, TN: Oak Ridge National Laboratory, 1979.
- [12] Shengjie Li. "Beta decay heat following U-235, U-238 and Pu-239 neutron fission". English. PhD thesis. 1997, p. 160. ISBN: 978-0-591-35164-4.
- [13] Edward H. Seabury. "Gamma ray decay heat measurements following U-238(n,f) and Pu-239(n,f)". English. PhD thesis. 1997, p. 110. ISBN: 978-0-591-27558-2.
- [14] A. Tobias et al. *Derivation of decay heat benchmarks for U235 and Pu239 by a least squares fit to measured data*. Tech. rep. 1989.
- [15] K. Baumung. *Messung der Nachzerfallsleistung von ^{235}U im Zeitbereich von 15 s bis 4000 s*. Technical Report KfK 3262. Kernforschungszentrum Karlsruhe, Dec. 1981.
- [16] J. L. Yarnell et al. *Decay heat from products of ^{235}U thermal fission by fast response boil-off calorimetry*. Technical Report LA-NUREG-6713. Los Alamos National Laboratory, 1977.
- [17] M. Lott et al. "Puissance résiduelle totale emise par les produits de fission thermique de ^{235}U ". In: *Journal of Nuclear Energy* 27 (1973), pp. 597–605.
- [18] A L Nichols et al. "Improving fission-product decay data for reactor applications: part I—decay heat". en. In: *Eur. Phys. J. A* 59.4 (Apr. 2023).
- [19] M.B. Chadwick et al. "ENDF/B-VII.1 Nuclear Data for Science and Technology: Cross Sections, Covariances, Fission Product Yields and Decay Data". In: *Nuclear Data Sheets* 112.12 (2011). Special Issue on ENDF/B-VII.1 Library, pp. 2887–2996. ISSN: 0090-3752. DOI: 10.1016/j.nds.2011.11.002.